

RSBI Toolkit for organising a *Beer and Science* event

Define the goals and audience:

A *Beer and Science* event may primarily focus on encouraging social interaction, with educational elements incorporated afterwards.

Identifying the target audience is crucial. You may target beer enthusiasts, science people, or a broader audience. This event could also be organized to students, providing them with an opportunity to showcase their research projects. It could also appeal to attendees of conferences or workshops, offering a relaxed setting for socializing and discussing science at the end of the day. Additionally, it could be designed for researchers to network and share ideas, or even open to the general public, organized by scientists. Therefore, defining the target audience is crucial.

Select the venue:

Choose a venue that can comfortably accommodate your anticipated audience and aligns with the event's theme. Options include breweries, science museums, pubs, or outdoor spaces. Ensure the venue offers necessary facilities for presentations or demonstrations, as well as ample room for socializing. Determine whether talks will utilize PowerPoint presentations with visuals, paper posters for schematic drawings, or if they will be informal discussions without multimedia aids.

For inaugural events, it's advisable to target a smaller audience to foster engagement. As you gain experience, gradually increase the number of participants to suit the space appropriately.

Organize the content and talk time:

Arrange the content for your event by selecting speakers who will address a predetermined theme. Additionally, determine the allotted time for each speaker's presentation, which can be either 3 or 5 minutes. Longer durations often lead to audience disengagement, so it's advisable to reserve more time for questions and discussions afterward.

Balance educational content with fun activities such as beer tasting, interactive demonstrations, or hands-on workshops to enhance the experience.

Secure the speakers:

Depending on the target audience and desired speakers, the speakers can be students, experienced researchers presenting to a general audience or to peers. There are two possibilities: inviting speakers on a specific topic or issuing a call for speakers where anyone interested can participate. If too many speakers register, a selection of speakers that best

aligns with the evening's topic can be made. Therefore, when a speaker registers for the event, they should fill out a form providing the title of their topic and a brief abstract consisting of 3-4 sentences. However, if too many speakers register, following a selection, the remaining registrants should be kindly invited to participate as audience or chairpersons.

Promote the event:

Prepare captivating promotional materials including flyers, social media posts, and emails to spark interest. Use targeted marketing to reach your audience by advertising on university platforms, engaging with science communities, and listing the event on local calendars. Estimate the expected number of participants to plan the venue more accurately.

Plan the logistics:

The event may be open to all attendees at no cost. Logistics arrangements with the venue can ensure minimal disruption during presentations. Attendees have the option to order drinks and select appetizers before the presentations start. Additionally, food orders can be placed to coincide with the estimated break time, allowing waitstaff to serve attendees promptly.

Day-of coordination:

On the day of the event, ensure early arrival to supervise setup and handle any unforeseen matters. Coordinate closely with speakers, suppliers, and volunteers to guarantee the event runs smoothly. Designate a chairperson to welcome speakers and participants, deliver introductory remarks, briefly introduce speakers, encourage participant interaction, and conclude the event. Follow up with attendees by sharing resources and information about future events.

Gather the feedback:

Gather input from attendees to assess the event's success and pinpoint areas for improvement. Utilize this feedback to refine future editions of your *Beer and Science* event, enhancing its appeal and enjoyment for participants. Distribute an online feedback form at the conclusion of the event, encouraging everyone to anonymously share their thoughts.

With these steps in mind, you should be well-equipped to organize a memorable Beer and Science event that entertains and educates your audience!